

Actionable Intelligence for Social Policy

Amy Hawn Nelson, PhD

Helping state and
local governments
collaborate and
responsibly use
data to improve
lives.

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THE ANNIE E. CASEY FOUNDATION

BILL & MELINDA
GATES *foundation*

AISP'S Role

We are:	We are not:
Data evangelists	Data holders or intermediaries
Connectors, community builders, thought partners, cheerleaders, and data sharing therapists	A vendor or vendor recommender
Focused on ethical data use for policy change	Focused on academic research

Our Network & Learning Community

- Network of 22 operational state and local integrated data systems
- Between our three Learning Community cohorts and other sites we support, 14 more sites well on their way

 Network Sites

 Developing Sites

What we do

Peer Network

Guidance & Standards

Training & Consulting

Advocacy & Communications

Actionable Research

INTRODUCTION TO

Data Sharing & Integration

CASE STUDY

How the Indiana Management Performance Hub's Data Capacity Helped Fuel COVID-19 Research and Response

A TOOLKIT FOR

Centering Racial Equity Throughout Data Integration

Building + Sustaining State Data Integration Efforts: Legislation, Funding, and Strategies

Our approach

Data sharing is as relational
as it is technical.

We don't just need to integrate data;
we need to integrate people.

When we talk about Integrated Data Systems, what do we mean?

- We're talking about people, not tech solutions.
- Efforts that routinely link administrative data across domains/agencies
- Efforts that curate data that is relevant and high quality
- Efforts that serve as a public utility (not research for research's sake)
- Efforts that have defined governance structures (data is only used for approved uses)

So why am I here?

Data Science programs often serve two important purposes for cross sector data integration.

- Universities are training staff. And Data Scientists who understand admn data reuse are essential to evidence-based policy making.
- Universities often serve as neutral 3rd parties to support data integration. Aka, Data Switzerland.

Quality Framework for IDS

Quality Framework for Integrated Data Systems

Governance

Legal

Technical

Capacity

Impact

Governance: Overview

Data governance is the people, policies, and procedures that support how data are used and protected. Data governance for a cross-sector data sharing effort can draw upon one agency's existing data governance practices, involve a separate set of policies and procedures, or be a hybrid of the two. Regardless of the approach taken, cross-sector governance policies and practices should be explicit and collaboratively agreed upon, rather than implicit and driven by any one partner.

Remember – data flow at the speed of trust. Cross-agency data governance is a way of institutionalizing trust to ensure that data use is legal, ethical, and a good idea.

Purpose, Mission, and Vision Driven

The mission and vision of a

Practical and Strategic

In order to determine the

Collaborative

Governance policies and procedures should be

Vegetables are good for us

People say they want:

- Clean, linked data to help evaluate programs and policies
- Data for standard reporting and analytics

Which means they actually need:

- A process for figuring out what projects should be conducted
- Deduplication and reconciliation of records
- Standard definitions of key concepts (“attendance”, “race/ethnicity”, “substantiated”) *across agencies!*
- High quality data
- Built fields they think already exist (flag for PreK enrollment or chronically absent)
- Documentation of all of the above
- People, households and families linked across agencies

The fun stuff:
20% of our
time

The
vegetables:
80% of our
time

Super fun
analysis!!!

Governance,
legal, data
cleaning, linking,
standardizing

Usable data

Insights that drive
change

People using and
owning their
agencies data

Thank you to Kim Paull, RI Data Ecosystem, for permission to reuse this content.

Data

Filename:	Tadzik.jpg
Author:	Piotr Kononow
Date:	August 15, 2016 6:40:10PM
File:	5,312 × 2,988 JPEG 15.9 megapixels 3,393,448 bytes (3.2 megabytes)
Camera:	Samsung SM-G920F 4.3 mm
Lens:	Max aperture f/1.9 (shot wide open) Auto exposure Program AE
Exposure:	1/402 sec f/1.9 ISO 40
Flash:	none

A satellite map view showing the location of the photo. A green arrow points to the balcony area where the cat was sitting. The map shows a residential area with buildings and streets.

Metadata

Metadata is essential for ethical use

OPEN DATA	RESTRICTED DATA	UNAVAILABLE DATA
<p>Data that can be shared openly, either at the aggregate or individual level, based on state and federal law. These data often exist in open data portals.</p>	<p>Data that can be shared, but only under specific circumstances with appropriate safeguards in place.</p>	<p>Data that cannot or should not be shared, either because of state or federal law, lack of digital format (paper copies only), or data quality or other concerns.</p>

See, <https://www.aisp.upenn.edu/introduction-to-data-sharing/>

Metadata is essential for ethical use

The Role of Data Owners, Data Stewards, and Data Custodians		
	Role in data sharing process	Role within agency
Data Owner	Accountable for the quality and security of the data and holds decision-making authority regarding access and use	Typically agency leadership that has signatory authority
Data Steward	Responsible for the governance of data, including metadata. Support established processes and policies for access and use	Typically the subject matter experts and data analysts that work with data
Data Custodian	Responsible for the technology used to store and transport data	Typically an IT person or team

See, <https://www.aisp.upenn.edu/introduction-to-data-sharing/>

Data life cycle

(Every project starts at a different place)

Project Overview

Mecklenburg County, Institute for Social Capital

Problem that we are trying to solve	Mecklenburg County did not have high quality, integrated data, that could be used to describe and better understand issues around housing instability and homelessness, and most importantly, monitor progress of issues over time.
Organizations involved	UNC Charlotte Urban Institute, Mecklenburg County, Homelessness Service Providers, Charlotte Mecklenburg Schools (members of the Housing and Homelessness Ecosystem, https://mecklenburghousingdata.org/ecosystem/)
Data used	(Restricted) homelessness and other social services administrative data that is shared, integrated, and deidentified through an extensive governance process and legal framework of ISC
Time span of project	2014-current, updated annually
Point in data life cycle the project starts (Planning, Data Collection, Access, Statistical Tools, Analysis, Reporting)	The entire data life cycle. Reporting and dissemination can be found here: https://mecklenburghousingdata.org/
Staffing	UNC Charlotte Urban Institute Staff, Graduate Students, Mecklenburg County Staff
Funding	Mecklenburg County
Impact	Report series provides longitudinal metrics, deep dives into content areas (e.g. evictions) and actionable data points to support the transition from unstable to stable housing.

Project Overview

Yoga 4 Change, Atlantic Beach, FL

Problem that we are trying to solve	The goal of the 2017 DSSG project was to help Yoga 4 Change organize their data and provide reports to support them in critical program decisions, including finding out which groups (veterans, incarcerated individuals, vulnerable youth, and substance abuse) show the most benefit from specific aspects of the yoga curricula.
Organizations involved	University of North Florida, Yoga 4 Change, Nonprofit Center of Northeast Florida, Jacksonville Jaguars, and EverBank.
Data used	Self-assessments for stress and mood levels to students in their classes before and after each session, and blood pressure as well as their heart rate data.
Time span of project	Initial period – summer of 2017. Developed software to collect data systematically through capstone projects. Continue to add features to aid program assessment data.
Point in data life cycle the project starts	Entire lifecycle
Staffing	UNF undergraduate and graduate students
Funding	Nonprofit Center of Northeast Florida
Impact	The report helped Yoga 4 Change obtain funding from various donors, which aided in expanding the program, recruiting more yoga instructors, and hiring a researcher to prove yoga therapy helps reduce stress and increase mood scientifically.

Project Overview

Inclusive
Development
International

THE UNIVERSITY OF
CHICAGO

Inclusive Development International

Problem that we are trying to solve	Development Finance Institutions (DFIs) invest large amount of money in projects around the world to help industrialize developing countries. The impact of these projects and their loan pipelines often lack transparency. We are developing a tool that allows researchers a central place to access data on these projects and better understand their impact.
Organizations involved	Inclusive Development International University of Chicago Data Science Institute
Data used	Project documents from the individual development banks (16 in total) Documents filed to accountability mechanisms by communities adversely effected
Time span of project	This project has been in development for 1 year
Point in data life cycle (Planning, Data Collection, Access, Statistical Tools, Analysis, Reporting)	When we started this project IDI was in the Data Collection phase. They worked frequently with this data, but research was slow and aggregation of information was time consuming.
Staffing	Data science resources from UC, and domain access to a domain expert at IDI
Funding	Project support was provided by the 11 th Hour Project.
Impact	This project not only dramatically speeds up the work of researchers at IDI but is open source and will be available to similar organizations around the world. This leads to greater transparency from the international development finance organizations and will highlight the impact their loans are having on local communities. Community members can also access the dashboard having easier access to information about complaints made about projects near them.

Project Overview

I2D2 Early Childhood Iowa Dashboard

Problem that we are trying to solve	Iowa's state agency leaders, program officers, regional directors who work in early childhood wanted more readily accessible data that combines national, state, and local sources and is available in a user-friendly format capable of producing useful reports and visualizations for various users
Organizations involved	Early Childhood Iowa and Iowa's Integrated Data System for Decision-Making (I2D2). ISU's Cooperative Extension System helped to identify and map 22 initial dashboard indicators, that were then updated and formalized by the DSPG team.
Data used	I2D2, local, state, and national data
Time span of project	Ongoing (DSPG program was 10 weeks)
Point in data life cycle the project starts (Planning, Data Collection, Access, Statistical Tools, Analysis, Reporting)	Iterative process- the core indicators are approved by the state board, and we provide recommendations on other options. The DSPG beta-version of the dashboard is being reviewed, feedback incorporated, and new data and tools developed.
Staffing	I2D2 core team, DSPG students
Funding	Early Childhood Iowa, Iowa Department of Public Health, I2D2, USDA
Impact	The ECI-I2D2 dashboard will serve many purposes, including providing useful data and insights to assist early childhood agencies in conducting needs assessments and preparing grant applications, aid agencies and entities in advocacy work, and inform policy-makers and legislators about the state of early childhood wellness in Iowa.

Project Overview

MIAMI-DADE
IDEAS
CONSORTIUM
FOR CHILDREN

INTEGRATING
DATA FOR
EFFECTIVENESS
ACROSS
SYSTEMS

Partnership for school readiness

Problem that we are trying to solve	What is descriptive picture of children participating in preschool programs in Miami-Dade County? Where are programs of quality located geographically? Does participation promote kindergarten readiness?
Organizations involved	Miami-Dade County Public Schools, Early Learning Coalition of Miami-Dade/Monroe Counties, Miami-Dade County Community Action Agency Head Start and Early Head Start, Early Intervention Part C, Florida Office of Early Learning, The Children's Trust, University of Miami
Data used	Enrollment, attendance, child/family demographics at registration, developmental assessments, kindergarten readiness screener, special education, CCDF subsidized funding categories, quality rating from QIS and child care registry
Time span of project	2013-2018
Point in data life cycle the project starts	Planning 2012-13; Data collection 2011-2015; Access with data sharing agreement 2015-16; Data integration & analysis 2016-2018; Reporting 2018 to present
Staffing	Research Director, Graduate Student, Data & computer scientist, Outreach and partnership facilitator, with Agency Governance Committee and data support Mentorship from AISP Learning Community Network
Funding	IES Research-practitioner grant (2014-2018) \$400,000 The Children's Trust (2018+ annual core \$150,000) UM internal grants (ULINK, 2019; 2020)
Impact	Legal, technical and governance infrastructure built capacity for future work. Needs assessment findings informed QIS deployment and resource allocation, baseline for measuring progress in reaching high need areas.

MIAMI-DADE
IDEAS
CONSORTIUM
FOR CHILDREN

INTEGRATING
DATA FOR
EFFECTIVENESS
ACROSS
SYSTEMS

Miami-Dade County Public Schools

Early Learning Coalition of Miami-Dade/Monroe

The Children's Trust

Miami-Dade County Head Start/Early HS (CAHSD)

Children's Registry and Information System (CHRIS)

University of Miami, Dept of Psychology

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The Children's Trust

U-LINK (UM Provost's Office for Research)

Spencer Foundation

Robert Wood Johnson Foundation

Our Partners

Questions?

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